

The 'triple whammy' of threats to coasts and the 'environment-tourism paradox' - the DAPSI(W)R(M) unifying framework for coastal management

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Abstract

The coastal environment is a complex system formed by interactions between ecological structure and functioning, physico-chemical processes and socio-economic systems. An increase in competing uses and users requires a holistic approach to coastal management which considers the environmental, economic and societal impacts of all activities. If managed sustainably, the marine environment will deliver a range of ecosystem services which lead to benefits for society. The problem-structuring DAPSI(W)R(M) (pronounced dap-see-worm) framework is used to assess the causes, consequences and responses to change in a holistic way. Drivers of basic human needs require Activities which lead to Pressures, the mechanisms of State change on the natural system which then leads to Impacts (on human Welfare). Those then require Responses (as management Measures). The framework is used here to address the so-called 'triple whammy' affecting coasts worldwide – of increased urbanisation and industrialisation, increased use of physical and biological resources (such as energy, space, fishes, etc) and a decreased resistance and resilience to climate change (including sea-level rise, increased storminess, etc). In giving lessons for coastal management worldwide, this risk assessment and management framework is applied to the Balneário Camboriú – SC (Brazil) coastline which shows most of the features of coastlines worldwide and which is a major development area for Brazil. It particularly shows what may be called the 'environment-tourism paradox' whereby excessive coastal tourism eventually damages the desirable features initially responsible for the tourism and creates tensions between tourists and local inhabitants as seen in tourism hotspots worldwide.

Introduction

The marine environment is a complex social-ecological system of interactions between morphological and physical structures, continuously varying physico-chemical processes and varying ecological structure and functioning (Smith et al., 2025). Superimposed on this dynamic ecosystem, the intensity of anthropogenic activities both varies and is increasing, and pressures from these activities may affect the natural environment and subsequently this may have a knock-on effect on society (Burdon, 2016; Burdon et al., 2018; Elliott and Kennish, 2024; Smith et al., 2025). This may be regarded as a continuum from the ecological structure and functioning to the societal aspects onto which is superimposed the effects of human activities (Elliott, 2023). Management of these aspects therefore requires a holistic approach that recognizes the complexity of the system and accommodates the diverse range of uses and users (Elliott et al., 2025; Smith et al., 2025).

This is particularly the case given the major aim in marine environmental management – to maintain and protect the ecological structure and functioning while at the same time ensure that it maintains ecosystem services from which society can obtain goods and benefits (Elliott, 2023). As such, integrated marine management needs to consider the environmental, economic and societal impacts of all activities (Puente-Rodríguez et al., 2015). The Ecosystem Approach, enshrined in the UN Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD, 2000), provides the 12 guiding principles for such an integrated management.

Fully achieving the Ecosystem Approach in marine management requires an interdisciplinary approach bridging the divide between the natural environment and society. In such a complex system, the approach requires a large level of detail and must be fully linked to an operational policy life cycle to ensure that measures reflect societal goals and objectives (Cormier et al., 2017; Elliott et al., 2020, 2025; Smith et al., 2025). It is recognized, however, that effective marine management requires the complexity of the marine system and the links between the environment and society to be firstly understood by managers, policymakers and stakeholders (Beaumont et al., 2007) and secondly carried out with their involvement (Newton and Elliott, 2016).

The DAPSI(W)R(M) approach (pronounced dap-see-worm) is a cause-consequence-response framework in which we assess, measure and monitor the Pressures, State changes and Impacts (on Welfare), and our Responses (using management Measures) then act on and manage the Drivers and Activities to prevent deleterious effects. Elliott et al. (2019) and Defeo and Elliott (2021) summarise threats to coasts and estuaries worldwide and present the 'triple whammy', i.e. three major threats (i) increased industrialisation and urbanisation; (ii) the increased use of physical (space, energy, water, etc.) and biological (fish, shellfish) resources, and (iii) the decreased resistance and resilience to climate change (temperature, acidification, storminess, species distribution changes, alien species, etc). Here we use the DAPSI(W)R(M) approach to interrogate the causes, consequences and solutions to these threats and use an example from the city of Balneário Camboriú and the coastline of Santa Catarina State, in southern Brazil (Fig. 1). However, it is emphasised that such a case-study has similarities with and lessons for coasts and especially tourism hotspots worldwide.

Coastal regions represent just 10% of the total available land mass (Barragán and De Andrés, 2015). Globally, 2.15 billion people reside in near-coastal zones, with 898 million inhabitants in low-elevation coastal zones immediately adjacent to the ocean (MacManus et al., 2021; Reimann et al., 2023). In 2000 there was a total urban land cover of 222,000 km² within 40km of the coast (Angel et al., 2011). Coastal cities play an integral role in supporting both national and global economic growth and development, but this creates a feedback loop which then stimulates urbanization (UN, 2011).

Urban expansion has recently increased especially by tourism, a unique resource combination at the interface of land and sea offering amenities such as water, beaches, scenic beauty, rich terrestrial and marine biodiversity, diversified cultural and historic heritage, healthy food and, usually, good infrastructure (Elliott et al., 2019). Coastal tourism and housing development in turn require infrastructure especially near to culturally important cities (European Environment Agency – EEA, 2011; Houimli, 2008).

Brazil is one of the fastest urban developing countries in Latin America and possibly globally in recent decades with its population growing exponentially from around 17.5 M in 1900 to around 212 M today. The urban population in 1940 was about 31.2 % (IBGE, 2019), rising to 67.6 % in 1980 (IBGE, 2019) and 84.3 % in 2017 (SC, 2017). The Brazilian coastal zone consists of 443 municipalities (Ordinance No. 461/2018), about 5.02 % of the Brazilian municipalities in 251,241 km² (2.95 % of the Brazilian territory) supporting 24.52 % of the population (IBGE, 2022). Coastal economic activities account for about 70 % of GDP (Brazil, 2007) with a megacity (Rio de Janeiro), and approx. 16 metropolitan areas (IBGE, 2018) along a 7367 km coastline.

The 'sun and beach economic segment' in Brazil correlates with annual coastal sunshine hours in attracting most of the global and national tourists due to tropical or Mediterranean climates. Hence mass tourism (Brazilian Ministry of Environment, 2008), via the 'summer season culture' custom, demands 'sun, sea and sand' for leisure and increasing urbanization. This changes the coasts from places of waste, of work, and housing for the poor, to a new status as therapeutically beneficial for health and then elegant and up-market places for leisure (Corbin, 1986). Hence, the development of iconic tourism areas such as the Copacabana beach, in Rio de Janeiro, for example, primarily a Carioca suburb, a distant neighbourhood where wealthy families vacationed or lived. Owning a property or vacationing on the seafront in many Brazilian cities thus became synonymous with status; the beach assuming the urban leisure function of the park (MMA, 2004).

In Brazil, however, this tourist migration led to deficiencies in urban infrastructure and services, contributing in many cases to the loss of quality. This is termed here the 'environment-tourism paradox' which we define as 'increasing tourism overcomes the limits of environmental, physical and social carrying capacity, thus leading to significant problems and conflicts in coastal municipalities and an eventual degradation of the features initially responsible for the tourism'. This review catalogues the development of one coastal area, Balneário Camboriú in Santa Catarina, and demonstrates this paradox against a background of the cause-consequence-response continuum. It is emphasised that

this paradox is currently well-illustrated in tourism hotspots worldwide, such as the Canary and Balearic Islands, Spain, where tensions between tourists and local inhabitants are featured on international news media (e.g. The Guardian, 2024).

CORREA (2016) recognized that beach spatial and social relationships directly reflect space creation and use, in that the beach is a privileged space in the choice of modern and postmodern societies (pace St Tropez and the French Riviera). The desirable attributes of the beach (i.e. not only 'to enjoy' but 'to be seen to enjoy'), thereby leading to increased urbanisation and necessary infrastructure. For example, the emergence of a wealthy middle class in the major urban centres especially in developing countries such as Brazil, such as Sao Paulo and Rio de Janeiro, led to the development of industrial, financial, commercial and agro-industrial activities. This then affected the less-developed coastal municipalities and created the notion of 'being urban is being modern'. As indicated below, this development, enhanced by the 'sun, sea and sand' culture, became incompatible with the existing environmental and cultural conditions of the coastal municipality.

Most Brazilian coastal municipalities from the 1950s were remote from the benefits of industrial progress and business generated by agro-industry. They were forced to market their landscape heritage, which, even when not occupied, ensured a guaranteed income through taxes guaranteed by real estate companies in the major urban centres (São Paulo, Rio de Janeiro, Porto Alegre, etc.).

Much of the Brazilian shoreline is eroding, albeit at variable rates and often associated with river mouths (Muehe, 2010) and beach erosion becomes a risk when buildings are constructed too close to the shore. With global warming, the State of Santa Catarina is predicted to experience increasing erratic weather patterns and storminess, as part of the southernmost portion of the Atlantic Forest. The average temperature will rise by 1 °C in summer and a 10 % increase in summer precipitation by 2040 (PBMC, 2012). The coast is highly vulnerable due to large urban densities living below 10 m. Such urban densities, although presenting relatively high Human Development Index (HDI) levels in relation to other Brazilian municipalities, are exposed to risk. The city Balneário Camboriú, for example, is located in a region critical for the incidence of extreme events, such as the 2004 Hurricane Catarina and severe inundations (in 2008, 2011, 2013) (Nicolodi and Petermann, 2010).